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Chemical, Functional and Antioxidant Properties of Moriche Palm (*Mauritia flexuosa*) Fruit Flours

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Abstract

In this study, the chemical, functional and antioxidant properties of Moriche Palm (*Mauritia flexuosa*) fruit flours, whole moriche palm fruit flour (WMPFF), defatted moriche palm fruit flour (DMPFF) and moriche palm fruit protein concentrate (MPFPC) were investigated using standard methods. Results showed that the flours contain all the essential amino acids

in substantial quantities. Moisture, fat and fibre content ranged from 3.55 ± 0.55 to $10.55 \pm 0.45\%$ to $1.43 \pm 0.72\%$ and 0.21 ± 0.07 to $0.78 \pm 0.06\%$ respectively while ash, protein and carbohydrate ranged from 0.87 ± 0.04 to $1.55 \pm 0.03\%$, 6.77 ± 0.77 to $40.32 \pm 1.54\%$ and 41.37 ± 1.45 to 64.97 ± 1.55 respectively. Results of analyses for functional properties showed that whole flour exhibited lower values for water and oil absorption capacities (112.4 ± 1.43 & $174.9 \pm 2.45\%$) while protein concentrate showed the highest values (189.4 ± 1.54 & $243.2 \pm 0.66\%$), respectively. Similarly, the foaming capacity and stability ranged from 69.5 ± 1.63 to $97.4 \pm 1.55\%$; emulsion capacity and stability ranged from 89.5 ± 0.87 to $89.4 \pm 0.55\%$ and 1.43 ± 0.05 to $3.32 \pm 0.06 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and least gelation concentration ranged from 7.00 ± 0.05 to $13 \pm 0.05\%$, respectively. Phytochemical data indicated that saponin, tannin and steroid contents of the samples ranged from 3.05 ± 0.05 to 24.04 ± 0.88 , 3.44 ± 0.32 to 15.43 ± 0.67 and 0.63 ± 0.08 to $1.34 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg/g}$, respectively. Total phenolic, alkaloid and flavanoid contents ranged from 7.43 ± 0.34 to $54.3 \pm 1.43 \text{ mgGAE/g}$, 4.66 ± 0.08 to $19.7 \pm 0.67\%$ and 6.44 ± 0.22 to $42.45 \pm 1.55 \text{ mgRUTIN/g}$, respectively. Results of the *in vitro* antioxidant properties showed that 1, 1-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical scavenging, metal chelation, hydroxyl radical scavenging and superoxide radical scavenging activities ranked lowest in WMPFF and highest in MPFPC and ranged from 36.7-55.3, 43.7-64.2, 13.9-35.7 and 17.6-32.4%, respectively. The results suggest that moriche palm fruit flour samples could be used in product development to improve nutrient content and as functional foods and nutraceutical ingredients for the prevention and management of chronic disease conditions. Moriche palm fruit flours contain substantial quantity of amino acids and have demonstrated significant sources of bioactive compounds, good antioxidant properties and significant functional properties thereby making them to be good sources of functional foods and nutraceuticals that provide an opportunity to improve the human health, reduce health care costs and support economic development in rural communities.

Keywords: moriche palm fruit, antioxidant properties, functional properties, amino acids, protein concentrate

Introduction

There is a global prevalence of human chronic degenerative diseases such as obesity, diabetes, cancer and cardiovascular diseases (Girgih *et al.*, 2013). These myriads of diseases have been traced to cellular oxidative stress resulting from excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and free radicals, which overwhelm the body's ability to regulate them (Girgih *et al.*, 2011).

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are highly reactive molecules that contain electron-deficient oxygen atoms. During normal physiological and metabolic processes in living things, oxygen is reduced to oxygen-derived free radicals such as superoxide, hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl (OH) and nitric oxide radicals. These unstable free radical species tend to stabilize themselves by scavenging loose electrons from biological macromolecules such as proteins, lipids, cell membranes and DNA present in healthy human cells, thus causing damage to cellular organelles (Gilgun-Sherki *et al.*, 2016) and may also promote lipid peroxidation in food systems (Gulcin, 2020). The destructive activities of these free radicals if allowed to proceed unchecked may cause irreparable damage to cells leading to the progression of chronic diseases such as obesity, diabetes, cancer, heart and kidney diseases (Sen *et al.*, 2010). Sources of free radicals in the body include exogenous factors such as cigarette smoke, pollutants, ultraviolet, infrared, visible light, X-rays, ozone, environmental

toxicants and chemotherapeutic inflammation (Lobo *et al.*, 2010; Zhao, Wang, *et al.*, 2016). Endogenous sources of free radicals have been reported to be from electron transport chain, peroxisomes, cytochrome P-450, NADPH, cyclooxygenase, lipoxygenase, and Fe^{2+} (Phaniendra *et al.*, 2015; Bisht & Dada, 2017). Free radicals are also the end-products of normal breathing and energy production within the body's cells. However, their accumulation leads to oxidative stress when there is imbalance between the generation of free radicals (ROS and RNS) and the antioxidant defense mechanisms (Sinha & Kumar Dabla, 2015). Excessive production of ROS may damage membranes, proteins, enzymes, and DNA resulting in the development of chronic disease conditions (Girgih *et al.*, 2011).

Fruits and vegetables are important sources of vitamins, dietary minerals, fibres, and antioxidative compounds. They are a rich source of biologically active compounds, known as phytochemicals, which are an essential and beneficial part of the human diet. Antioxidants are abundant phytochemicals that prevent some of the processes involved in the development of various degenerative disorders and diseases, including cancer and cardiovascular diseases. Recent research has, therefore, become increasingly interested in the search for natural antioxidants from natural origins for use in the treatment and control of several human health disorders and diseases (Felhi *et al.*, 2016).

Moriche palm fruits also known as *aguaje* (in Peru) *buriti* (in Colombia) and *ichor* (in Tiv, Benue State of Nigeria) are consumed by both adults and children. Research has shown that it has a high content of β -carotene - vitamin A precursor and reasonable quantity of other important phenolic compounds (Vásquez-Ocmín *et al.*, 2010). However, few research works have been carried out on moriche palm fruit despite the fact that, there are a lot of these fruits especially in Nigeria and in Benue State in particular. This implies that the fruit is grossly underutilized, especially for the development of functional ingredients. Therefore, the main objectives of this study were to determine the chemical composition, functional and antioxidant properties of whole moriche palm fruit flour, defatted moriche palm fruit flour and moriche palm fruit protein concentrate.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The ripe moriche palm fruits were purchased on the palm tree from Mbashar village located in Mbagbera district, Vandeikya Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Pepsin (porcine gastric mucosa), pancreatin (porcine pancreas), trichloroacetic acid (TCA), 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), Triton X-100, hydrogen peroxide, 1,10-phenanthroline, ferrous sulfate, potassium ferricyanide, ferrous chloride, 3-(2-pyridyl)-5,6-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazine-4',4''-disulfite acid sodium salt (ferrozine) and reduced glutathione (GSH) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO).

Preparation of whole moriche palm fruit flour (WMPFF)

Whole moriche palm fruit flour was prepared according to methods described by Vásquez-Ocmín (2010) with slight modifications. These fruits were randomly collected from different moriche palm trees of the same species from the same locality. The collected fruits were put in separate plastic containers and then washed and disinfected with a continuous water flow.

Damaged or discoloured fruits were discarded. Water at 60°C was added to each of the containers for an hour, with the purpose of removing the epicarp (the husk); the mesocarp (pulp) and seed were separated by hand. The mesocarp (pulp) obtained was sundried using a tray on a raised platform for 6-7 hours. The dried mesocarp was stored in airtight containers till when needed for use. The dried mesocarp was then milled using an electric blender to obtain the whole moriche palm fruit flour. The whole meal was then sieved using 8.0µm sieve. The sieved meal was then packaged in airtight polythene bags until needed for further analysis and for preparation of defatted meal and protein concentrate.

Preparation of defatted moriche palm fruit flour (DMPFF)

The ground WMPFF was defatted according to the procedure used previously by Girgih *et al.* (2016) by mixing 1 g of WMPFF with 10 ml of acetone. The mixture was stirred in a fume hood for 3 h and decanted followed by second and third consecutive acetone extractions of the AWF residue. The resulting DMPFF residue was air-dried overnight in the fume hood to produce DMPFF and stored to be used for further studies.

Preparation of moriche palm fruit protein concentrate (MPFPC)

The MPFPC was prepared by a method modified by Gbadamosi *et al.* (2012). A known weight (50 g) of the defatted flour was dispersed in distilled water (2,000 ml) to give final flour to water ratio of 1:10. The dispersion was then gently stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 10 min to form a suspension, after which the pH of the resultant slurry was adjusted with 0.1 M HCl to the point at which the protein was least soluble (pH 4; a value obtained from preliminary solubility results of the defatted flour during preliminary investigation) to precipitate the proteins. The precipitation process was allowed to proceed with gentle stirring for 4 h keeping the pH constant. Soluble carbohydrates (oligosaccharides) and minerals were removed by centrifugation at 3,500 × g for 30 min using a centrifuge (Bosch, TDL-5, United Kingdom). The precipitate (concentrate) was afterward washed twice with distilled water to remove the residual minerals and soluble carbohydrates, and the pH is later adjusted with 0.1 M NaOH to 7.0 for neutralization and then centrifuged at 3,500 × g for 10 min. The resultant precipitate (concentrate) was collected and dried in an oven at 45 °C for 8 h (Uniscope SM9053 Laboratory Oven, Singerfriend, England) and kept in an air-tight container for further analysis.

Amino acid composition of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

Amino acid composition of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined following the method described by Gbadamosi *et al.* (2012) using S433Amino Acid Analyzer (SYKAM, Eresing, Germany). Samples were freeze-dried and then hydrolyzed for 24 h at 110 °C with 6 M HCl. After hydrolysis, the samples were freeze-stored in sodium citrate buffer at pH 2.2. When ready for analysis, 50 µL of the hydrolysates were directly injected into the analyser. Tryptophan was determined separately by hydrolysis of the sample with sodium hydroxide. Cysteine and methionine were determined after performic acid oxidation prior to hydrolysis in 6 M HCl, and measured as cysteic acid and methionine sulphone respectively (Girgih *et al.* 2011)

Moisture content

Moisture content of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined by the standard AOAC (2000) official method by drying about 3 g (W_1) of the samples in a hot air-oven

(Uniscope, SM9053, England) at 105 ± 1 °C until constant weight (W_2) was obtained. The sample was removed from the oven, cooled in a desiccator and weighed. This continued until constant weight was obtained. The result was expressed as percentage of dry matter.

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100$$

W_1 = weight of flour before drying

W_2 = weight of flour after drying

Crude fat content

Crude fat of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined by the AOAC (2005) method using Soxhlet apparatus (Sunbim, India). About 5 grams (W_3) of the ground sample was placed into a thimble which was placed inside Soxhlet extractor and n-hexane was poured into a pre-weighed round bottom flask (W_2), used to extract the oil from the sample. The extraction was carried out for about 6 h. The solvent was removed from the extracted oil by distillation. The oil in the flask was further dried in a hot-air oven at 90 °C for 30 minutes to remove residual organic solvent and moisture. This was cooled in a desiccator and flask and its content weighed (W_1). The quantity of oil obtained was expressed as percentage of the original sample used using equation (iii) given below:

$$\text{Ether extract (\%)} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_3} \times 100$$

Crude fibre content

Crude fibre content of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined using the method described by AOAC (2005). Two grams (W_3) of sample was dissolved in 200 ml of 1.25 % (*v/v*) sulphuric acid in a conical flask and was placed on a hot plate and boiled for 30 min. The content was filtered using filter paper (Whatman No.1) and the residue on the filter paper was washed with 70 ml distilled water. The washed residue was transferred back into the flask and about 200 ml 1.25 % (*w/v*) NaOH is added and boiled for 30 min. The content was filtered as described earlier and the residue obtained was washed with distilled water and then filtered again using filter paper (Whatman No.1). The residue was then transferred to an ashing dish and dried at 130 °C for 2 h, cooled in a desiccator and weighed (W_1). This was then ashed at 550 °C inside the muffle furnace chamber (Carbolite AAF1100, United Kingdom) for 30 min, cooled and reweighed (W_2). The ash obtained was subtracted from the residue and the difference expressed as percentage of the starting material as shown in equation below.

$$Cf = \left(\frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_3} \right) \times 100$$

where,

Cf = Crude fibre (%)

W_1 = mass of crucible with the dried residue (g)

W_2 = mass of crucible with the ash (g)

W_3 = mass of sample(g)

Crude protein content

The protein content of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined using the AOAC (2000) method. The ground sample (0.20 g) was weighed into a Kjeldahl flask. Ten millilitre of concentrated sulphuric acid was added followed by one Kjeltex tablet. The mixture was digested on a heating racket to obtain a clear solution. The digestate was cooled and made up to 75ml with distilled water and transferred onto Kjeldahl distillation unit followed by the addition of 50 mL of 40 % sodium hydroxide solution. The mixture was then distilled and the ammonia formed in the mixture was subsequently distilled into 25 ml, 2 % boric acid solution containing 0.5 ml of the mixture of 100 ml of bromocresol green solution (prepared by dissolving 100 mg of bromocresol green in 100 ml of methanol) and 70 ml of methyl red solution (prepared by dissolving 100 mg of methyl red in 100 ml methanol) as indicators. The distillate collected was titrated with 0.05M HCl. Blank determination was carried out by excluding the sample from the above procedure.

$$\text{Crude protein (\%)} = \frac{1.401 \times M \times F (\text{ml titrant} - \text{ml blank})}{\text{sample weight}}$$

$$M = \text{Molarity of acid used} = 0.05$$

$$F = \text{kjeldahl factor} = 6.25$$

Ash content

Ash content of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined by the official AOAC (2000) method using muffle furnace (Carbolite AAF1100, United Kingdom). About 2 g (W_3) of the samples were weighed into a pre-weighed ashing crucible (W_2) and placed in the muffle furnace chambers at 550 °C until the samples turned into ashes usually within 5 h. The crucibles were removed, cooled in a desiccator and weighed (W_1). Ash content was expressed as the percentage of the weight of the original sample as shown in equation below.

$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = \left(\frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_3} \right) \times 100$$

$$W_1 = \text{weight of crucible + ash}$$

$$W_2 = \text{weight of empty crucible}$$

$$W_3 = \text{weight of sample}$$

Carbohydrate content

Carbohydrate content was expressed as a percentage of the difference between the addition of other proximate components and 100.

$$\text{Carbohydrate (\%)} = 100 - (\text{moisture content} + \text{ash content} + \text{crude protein} + \text{crude fibre} + \text{crude fat})$$

Oil absorption capacity (OAC)

Oil absorption capacity of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined by the centrifugal method elicited by Beuchat (1977) with slight modifications. One gram of sample was mixed with 10 ml of pure canola oil for 60 secs, the mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min at room temperature, centrifuged at 4000 g for 30 min and the oil that separated was carefully decanted and the tubes were allowed to drain at a 45° angle for 10 min and then weighed. Oil absorption was expressed as a percentage increase of the sample weight.

Water absorption capacity (WAC)

The WAC was determined at room temperature and at temperatures ranging between 60 to 90°C using a combination of the AACC (1995) method and those of Sosulski (1962) and Rutkowski and Kozłowska (1981). A 2 g sample was dispersed in 20 ml of distilled water. The contents were mixed for 30 s every 10min using a glass rod and after mixing five times, centrifuged at 4000 g for 20 min. The supernatant was carefully decanted and then the contents of the tube were allowed to drain at a 45° angle for 10 min and then weighed. The water absorption capacity was expressed as percentage increase of the sample weight.

Least gelation concentrations (LGC) of samples

The Least Gelation Concentration (LGC) of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined according to the method of Adebisi and Aluko (2011) by suspending the protein samples in water at different concentrations (2% to 20%, w/v, protein weight basis). The mixture was vortexed, placed in a water bath at 95 °C for 1 h, cooled rapidly under tap water and left in the refrigerator (4 °C) for 14 h. The sample concentration at which the gel did not slip when the tube was inverted was taken as the LGC.

Foaming capacity and stability

Foam capacity and foam stability of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined by a modification of the method described by Chavan *et al.* (2001). Approximately 500 mg of protein sample was dispersed in 100 ml of distilled water. The solution was then homogenized for 2 min using a blender (O'Qlink, China) set at high speed 5_{\max} then poured into 250 ml measuring cylinder. The percentage ratio of the volume increase to that of the original volume of protein solution in the measuring cylinder was calculated and expressed as foam capacity or whippability. Foam stability was expressed as percentage of the volume of foam remaining in the measuring cylinder to that of the original volume after 30 min of quiescent period.

$$\text{Foaming capacity (\%)} = \frac{V_2 - V_1}{V_1} \times 100 \quad (3.5)$$

$$\text{Foaming stability (\%)} = \frac{V_3 - V_1}{V_1} \times 100 \quad (3.6)$$

$$V_1 = \text{volume before whipping (ml)}$$

$$V_2 = \text{volume after whipping (ml)}$$

$$V_3 = \text{volume after standing (ml)}$$

Emulsifying activity and stability index

The emulsifying activity index (EAI) of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined by a modified turbidimetric method described by Pearce and Kinsella (1978). About 500 mg sample was dispersed in 80 mL of distilled water. The sample slurry will be mixed with 20 ml of vegetable oil, and the mixture was homogenized using a blender (VLC, Sapphire, England) set at high speed for 60 s. Fifty microlitres of the aliquot of the emulsion was transferred from the bottom of the blender after homogenization and mixed with 5 ml of 0.1 % sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) solution. The absorbance of the diluted emulsions was measured at 500 nm using spectrophotometer (722-2000 Spectronic 20D, England) in 1 cm path length cuvette. The absorbance was read initially, after that turbidity and EAI will be calculated using the following formula

$$T = \frac{2.303 \times A}{I}$$

Where T = turbidity, A = absorbance at 500 nm and I = path length of cuvette (cm).

The emulsion activity index (EAI) will then be calculated as:

$$\text{Emulsifying activity index (m}^2/\text{g)} = \frac{2 \times T}{0.2 \times C} \quad (3.3b)$$

where T is the turbidity, C is the weight of protein per unit volume of aqueous phase before the emulsion is formed (g/ml); 0.2 is the volumetric fraction of oil and 2 is a constant. The emulsion stability index (ESI) was determined after the emulsion was allowed to stay for 10 minutes and the absorbance of the mixture was read at 500 nm and calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Emulsion stability index} = \frac{\text{EAI at 10 min}}{\text{EAI at 0 min}} \times 100$$

Determination of total phenolic concentration (TPC)

Determination of total phenolic content of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were carried out using Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol reagent reaction as described by Hoffman and Singleton (1977). The calibration curve solutions were prepared by pipetting 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0 ml of gallic acid standard solution (1.0 mg/ml gallic acid) in triplicate into clean dried test tubes. Each test tube was made up to 1.0 ml with distilled water. To each of the test tube was added 1.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent, incubated at room temperature for 5 min followed by the addition of 1.5 ml of 10% (w/v) NaHCO_3 solution to give a total volume of 4.0 ml. The reaction mixtures were further incubated for an additional one and half hours and the absorbance is read at 725 nm against blank containing all reagents except the standard gallic acid which is replaced with distilled water. The standard curve is obtained by plotting absorbance against the concentration. The determination of total phenol in methanolic extract of *A. esculentus* was done by pipetting 0.5 ml each of 1 mg/ml methanolic extract into clean dry test tubes in triplicate. The volumes were adjusted to 1.0 ml with distilled water. To each of the tubes was added 1.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent. The reaction mixture was incubated at room temperature for 5 min. To the reaction mixture was added 1.5 ml of 10% (w/v) NaHCO_3 solution. The reaction mixture was incubated for one and half hours (1½ hr). The absorbance was read at 725nm against blank containing the extract and all reagents except Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent which was replaced with distilled water. The concentrations of the phenolics in the extract is extrapolated from standard curve and expressed as milligram gallic acid equivalent per g of extract (mg GAE/g extract).

Determination of total flavonoid concentration

The concentration of flavonoids in the extracts of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined spectrophotometrically according to the procedure of Navabi *et al.* (2013). The extract (0.01 g) was dissolved in about 5 ml of extraction solvent and made up to 20 ml to give a final concentration of 0.5 mg/ml. To clean dry test tubes (in triplicate) will be pipetted 0.5 ml of working solution of the sample and diluted with 4.5 ml distilled water. To each test tube was then added 0.3 ml of 5% (w/v) NaNO_2 , 0.3 ml of 10% AlCl_3 and 4 ml of 4% (w/v) NaOH . The reaction mixtures were incubated at room temperature for 15 min. The absorbance was read at 500nm against reagent blank containing all reagents except the

extract or standard quercetin in the case of standard curve solutions. The standard calibration curve was prepared by pipetting 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 ml of 1 mg/ml quercetin (1 mg / ml of quercetin standard solution) into clean dry test tubes. The volumes were made up to 5 ml with distilled water. To each of the tubes was added 0.3 ml of 5% (w/v) NaNO_2 , 0.3 ml of 5% (w/v) AlCl_3 and 4 ml of 4% (w/v) NaOH . The reaction mixture was incubated at room temperature for 15 min. Absorbance is taken at 500nm and was plotted against the concentration to give the standard calibration curve. The concentrations of the flavonoids in the extract were extrapolated from standard calibration curve and expressed as milligram rutin equivalent per g of extract (mg RUTIN/g extract).

Tannin determination

0.2g of finely ground samples of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were weighed into a 50ml sample bottle. 10ml of 70% aqueous acetone was added and properly covered. The bottle was put in an ice bath shaker and shaken for 2hours at 300 °C. Each solution was then centrifuge and the supernatant stored in ice. 0.2ml of each solution was pipetted into the test tube and 0.8ml of distilled water was added. Standard tannin acid solutions were prepared from a 0.5mg/ml of the stock and the solution was made up to 1ml with distilled water. 0.5ml of FolinCiocateau reagent was added to both sample and standard followed by 2.5ml of 20% Na_2CO_3 . The solution was then vortexed and allowed to incubate for 40 minutes at room temperature, its absorbance was read at 725nm against a reagent blank concentration of the same solution from a standard tannic acid curve was prepared (Makkar and Goodchild. 1996).

Saponin determination

The spectrophotometric method of Brunner (1994) was used for Saponin determination. 2g of the finely ground samples of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were weighed into a 250ml beaker and 100ml of Isobutyl alcohol was added. Shaker was used to shake the mixture for 5 hours to ensure uniform mixing. The mixture was filtered with No 1 Whatman filter paper into 100ml beaker containing 20ml of 40% saturated solution of magnesium carbonate (MgCO_3). The mixture obtained again was filtered through No 1 Whatman filter paper to obtain a clean colourless solution. 1ml of the colourless solution was taken into 50ml volumetric flask using pipette, 2ml of 5% iron (iii) chloride (FeCl_3) solution was added and made up to the mark with distilled water. It was allowed to stand for 30 minutes for the colour to develop. The absorbance was read against the blank at 380nm.

Alkaloid determination

5g of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were weighed into a 250ml beaker and 200ml of 10% acetic acid in ethanol was added and allowed to stand for 4min. This was filtered and extract was concentrated on a water bath to one quarter of the original volume. Concentrated ammonium hydroxide added drop wise to the extract until the precipitation was completed. The whole solution was allowed to settle and the precipitated was collected and washed with dilute ammonium hydroxide and then filtered. The residue was the alkaloid which was dried and weighed Harbone(1973).

$$\% \text{ALKALOID} = \text{weight before-weight after/weight before} *100$$

Quantitative estimation of steroids

Sample 2 g of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were extracted using 20 ml of distilled water and stirred for 2 h, then filtered with filter paper. 1ml of test extract of steroid solution was transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks. Sulphuric acid (4N, 2ml) and iron (III) chloride (0.5% w/v, 2 ml), were added, followed by potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) solution (0.5% w/v, 0.5 ml). The mixture was heated in a water-bath maintained at $70 \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 minutes with occasional shaking and diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 780 nm against the reagent blank (Mhadu *et al.*, 2016).

DPPH radical scavenging activity (DRSA) assay

The scavenging activity of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined using a previously described method (Aluko & Monu, 2003) with slight modifications for a 96-well clear flat-bottom plate. Peptide samples were dissolved in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.0 containing 1% (w/v) Triton X-100. DPPH was dissolved in methanol to a final concentration of 100 μM . Peptide samples (100 μL) were mixed with 100 μL of the DPPH solution in the 96-well plate to a final assay concentration of 1 mg/mL and incubated at room temperature in the dark for 30 min. The absorbance values of the control (Ac) and samples (As) were measured at 517 nm. The control consisted of sodium phosphate buffer in place of the peptide sample while GSH was used as the positive control. The percent DPPH radical scavenging activity of the samples was determined using the following equation:

$$\text{DPPH radical scavenging activity (\%)} = [(Ac - As) / Ac] \times 100$$

Superoxide radical scavenging activity (SRSA) assay

The WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were measured according to a previously described method (Xie *et al.*, 2008). An aliquot of 1 mg/ml of peptide samples or GSH (80 μl in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer containing 1 mM EDTA, pH 8.3) was mixed with 80 μl of the buffer in a clear bottom 96-well plate. Then, 40 μl of 1.5 mM pyrogallol dissolved in 10 mM HCl was added to each well. The reaction rate ($\Delta A/\text{min}$) was measured immediately at 420 nm for 4 min at room temperature using the buffer as a control. The SRSA was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Superoxide radical scavenging activity (\%)} = \{[(\Delta A/\text{min})_c - (\Delta A/\text{min})_s] / (\Delta A/\text{min})_c\} \times 100$$

where c and s represent control and sample, respectively.

Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity (HRSA) assay

The Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were determined based on a previously reported method (De Avellar *et al.*, 2004). Peptide samples and 3 mM of 1,10-phenanthroline were separately dissolved in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). FeSO_4 (3 mM) and 0.01% (v/v) hydrogen peroxide were both separately dissolved in distilled water. An aliquot (50 μl) of peptide samples (equivalent to a final assay concentration of 1 mg/ml) or buffer (control) was first added to a clear, flat bottom 96-well plate followed by 50 μl of 1, 10-phenanthroline and then 50 μl of FeSO_4 . To initiate the Fenton reaction, 50 μl of hydrogen peroxide was added to the mixture, covered and incubated at 37°C for 1h with shaking. The absorbance was measured using a spectrophotometer at 536 nm at 10 min intervals for 1 hr. The HRSA was then calculated using the reaction rate ($\Delta A/\text{min}$) as follows:

$$\text{Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity (\%)} = \{[(\Delta A/\text{min})_c - (\Delta A/\text{min})_s] / (\Delta A/\text{min})_c\} \times 100$$

where c and s represent control and sample, respectively.

Metal Chelating activity (MCA) assay

The metal chelating activity of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were measured using a modified method of Xie *et al.* (2008). Peptide sample solution or GSH (final assay concentration of 1 mg) was combined with 0.05 mL of 2 mM FeCl₂ and 1.85 mL double distilled water in a reaction tube. Ferrozine solution (0.1 mL of 5 mM) was added and mixed thoroughly. The mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 10 min from which an aliquot of 200 μ L was removed and added to a clear bottom 96-well plate. A control was also conducted by replacing the sample with 1 mL of double distilled water. The absorbance values of (Ac) and (As) at 562 nm were measured using a spectrophotometer and the metal chelating activity of the sample was compared to that of GSH. The percentage chelating effect (%) was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Metal chelating activity (\%)} = [(Ac - As) / Ac] \times 100$$

Ferric ion reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay

The WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC samples were measured according to a previously reported method (Zhang *et al.*, 2008), which was modified as follows. Peptide samples (250 μ L) dissolved in 0.2 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 6.6 or control (250 μ L of buffer) were mixed with 250 μ L of same buffer and 250 μ L of 1% (w/v) potassium ferricyanide solution. The peptide concentration in the assay mixture was 1 mg/ml and the mixture was heated at 50°C and incubated for 20 min. After incubation, 250 μ L of 10% (w/v) aqueous TCA was added. Thereafter, 250 μ L of peptide/TCA mixture was combined with 50 μ L of 0.1% (w/v) ferric chloride and 200 μ L of double distilled water and allowed to stand at room temperature for 10 min. The solution was then centrifuged at 1,000 $\times g$ and 200 μ L of the clear supernatant transferred to a 96-well plate for determination of the absorbance of the supernatant at 700 nm.

Statistical analysis

Proximate composition, functional, phytochemical and antioxidant assays were conducted in triplicate and analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The means were compared by Duncan's multiple range test and significant differences accepted at $p < .05$.

Results and Discussion

Amino acid composition of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

The functionality and physiological activities of protein peptides have been reported to be partly dependent on the amino acid composition and sequence (Karami & Akbari-Adergani, 2019; Sánchez & Vázquez, 2017). Table 1 shows the amino acid composition of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC. Moriche palm fruit protein like Sesame, soy and pea proteins (Fasuan *et al.*, 2018; Aondona *et al.*, 2020) contained all the 20 amino acids in differing proportions. It was also observed that the contents of certain amino acids increased with processing. For example, the total amount of negatively charged amino acids combined content (aspartic acid + asparagine (ASX) and glutamic acid + glutamine (GLX) in the WMPFF increased from 22.94 to 27.65 and 25.09 % for DMPFF and MPFPC respectively.

TABLE 1: Amino acid composition of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

Amino acids	WMPFF	DMPFF	MPFPC
LEU	13.83	10.55	9.82
LYS	8.93	6.73	6.93
ILE	3.94	3.23	2.93
PHE	1.23	3.24	5.44
TRY	2.33	2.18	2.08
VAL	8.33	6.65	4.87
MET	3.12	2.97	2.55
PRO	1.22	5.03	5.33
ARG	2.38	5.64	6.88
TYR	2.64	4.99	6.43
HIS	2.93	2.33	3.07
CYS	0.98	1.23	1.55
ALA	4.33	4.74	4.88
GLX	4.83	13.33	15.95
GLY	7.55	3.21	4.55
THR	6.88	3.21	2.14
SER	6.44	6.42	5.46
ASX	18.11	14.32	9.14
HAA	41.95	44.81	45.88
PCAA	14.24	14.70	16.88
NCAA	22.94	27.65	25.09
AAA	6.20	10.41	13.95
EAA	51.52	41.09	39.83
SCAA	4.10	4.20	4.10

Abbreviations: AA = amino acid. ASX = aspartic acid + asparagine; GLX = glutamic acid + glutamine; Combined total of hydrophobic amino acids (HAA) = Ala, Val, Ile, Leu, Tyr, Phe, Trp, Pro, Met, and Cys; positively charged amino acids (PCAA) = Arg, His, Lys; Negatively charged amino acids (NCAA) = ASX and GLX; Aromatic amino acids (AAA) = Phe, Trp, and Tyr; EAA = histidine, isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, threonine, tryptophan and valine; SCAA= MET and CYS

The presence of high amounts of negatively charged amino acids (NCAA) is a beneficial antioxidant quality, as these amino acids possess free electrons that can be donated to neutralize and limit the destructive tendency of free radicals. Previous reports have shown that NCAAs have strong antioxidant effects due to the presence of excess electrons, which can easily be donated during interaction with free radicals (Da Rocha *et al.*, 2018; Girgih *et al.*, 2014). Higher contents (6% and 7%) of Arg were found in the DMPFF and MPFPC respectively when compared to WMPFF (2%), representing an increase of about 137% – 189%. Such an increase of Arg content due to processing is a positive development as the presence of substantial amounts of this amino acid could serve as precursor for the production nitric oxide (NO), which promotes vasodilation via the enzyme endothelial nitric oxide synthesis. The inadequate production of NO by the body has been reported to be responsible for elevated blood pressure in both human and animal studies (Khalaf *et al.*,

2019). The combined contents of hydrophobic amino acids (HAA) were highest in the processed products (DMPFF & MPFPC) (44.81% & 45.88%) when compared to that of WMPFF (42 %). The presence of high amounts of HAA in the processed MPFF offers properties that are able to promote lipid interactions, which enhance entry of the peptides into target organs via hydrophobic associations (Sarmadi & Ismail, 2010). Processing of WMPFF into DMPFF and MPFPC increased the content of aromatic amino acids (AAA). The percentage of the aromatic amino acid (AAA) content was lowest in the WMPFF (6 %) but increased to 10 and 14% for DMPFF and MPFPC respectively. The presence of a benzene ring with several side chain groups contributes to metal chelation ability, which prevents metal-catalyzed production of free radicals (Rathore & Gupta, 2010).

Proximate composition of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

The results of the moisture content, fat, fibre, ash, protein and carbohydrates of the whole moriche palm fruit flour, defatted moriche palm fruit flour and moriche palm fruit protein concentrate are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2: Proximate Composition of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

Composition	WMPFF	DMPFF	MPFPC
Moisture (%)	10.5 ^a ±0.45	6.54 ^b ±0.55	3.55 ^c ±0.55
Fat (%)	38.98 ^a ±0.44	5.33 ^b ±0.08	1.43 ^c ±0.72
Fibre (%)	0.78 ^a ±0.06	0.54 ^a ±0.03	0.21 ^b ±0.07
Ash (%)	1.55 ^a ±0.03	1.19 ^a ±0.44	0.87 ^b ±0.04
Protein (%)	6.77 ^c ±0.77	21.43 ^b ±1.34	40.32 ^a ±1.54
Carbohydrate (%)	41.37 ^c ±1.45	64.97 ^a ±1.55	53.62 ^b ±1.56

Values are means± S.D triplicate determinations. Means within each row not followed by the same superscript letters are significantly different (p<0.05), WMPFF= whole moriche palm fruit flour, DMPFF = defatted moriche palm fruit flour and MPFPC = moriche palm fruit protein concentrate

Moisture, fat and fibre content ranged from 3.55±0.55 to 10.55±0.45% to 1.43±0.72% and 0.21±0.07 to 0.78±0.06% respectively while ash, protein and carbohydrate ranged from 0.87±0.04 to 1.55±0.03%, 6.77±0.77 to 40.32±1.54% and 41.37±1.45 to 64.97±1.55 respectively. There were significant (p<0.05) differences in the moisture content of the three moriche palm fruit products with whole moriche palm fruit flour having the highest value (10.55±0.45) and moriche palm fruit protein concentrate having the lowest value (3.55±0.55). There were also significant (p<0.05) differences in the values for fat, protein and carbohydrate content for the WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC.

Functional properties of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

The results of the functional properties of the WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3: Functional properties of moriche palm fruit flours

Parameter	WMPFF	DMPFF	MPFPC
Water absorption capacity (%)	174.93 ^c ±2.45	199.43 ^b ±0.78	243.22 ^a ±0.66
Oil absorption capacity (%)	112.44 ^c ±1.43	164.33 ^b ±1.43	189.43 ^a ±1.54
Foaming capacity (%)	69.54 ^c ±1.63	74.32 ^b ±1.11	89.44 ^a ±0.55
Foaming stability (%)	89.54 ^c ±0.87	93.22 ^b ±0.89	97.43 ^a ±1.55
Emulsion capacity (m²/g)	1.43 ^c ±0.05	2.34 ^b ±0.06	3.32 ^a ±0.06
Emulsion stability (%)	68.43 ^c ±1.53	74.32 ^b ±1.43	78.43 ^a ±1.43
Least gelation concentration (%)	7.00 ^b ±0.05	13.00 ^a ±0.05	13.00 ^a ±0.05

Values are means± S.D triplicate determinations. Means within each row not followed by the same superscript letters are significantly different (p<0.05).

KEY: MPFWF = *Moriche palm fruit whole flour*; MPFDF = *moriche palm fruit defatted flour*; MPFPC = *Moriche palm fruit protein concentrate*

From the results it can be seen that Water absorption capacity and oil absorption capacity ranged from 174.93±2.45 to 243.22±0.66% and 112.44±1.43 to 189.43±1.54% respectively while foaming capacity and foaming stability ranged from 69.54±1.63 to 97.43±1.55% respectively. Emulsion capacity and Emulsion stability ranged from 89.54±0.87 to 89.44±0.55% and 1.43±0.05 to 3.32±0.06m²/g respectively. Least gelation concentration ranged from 7.00±0.05 to 13±0.05%. Water absorption capacity or characteristics represent the ability of a product to associate with water under conditions where water is limited (Singh, 2001). Water absorption capacity was highest in MPFPC (243.22±0.66%) followed by DMPFF (199.43±0.78%), and WMPFF (174.93±2.45%). The highest water absorption capacity in the MPFPC could be attributed to its higher amount of protein. The highest value of Oil Absorption Capacity was observed for MPFPC (189.43±1.54%) followed by DMPFF (164.33±1.4 %) and lowest for WMPFF (112.44±1.43%). The water and oil binding capacity of food protein depend upon the intrinsic factors like amino acid composition, protein conformation and surface polarity or hydrophobicity (Suresh and Samsher, 2013). MPFPC having highest oil absorption capacity could serve well than the WMPFF and DMPFF as flavour retainer. The ability of the proteins of these flours to bind with oil makes them useful in food systems where optimum oil absorption is desired. This makes these flours have potential functional uses in foods. The oil absorption capacity also makes the

flours suitable in facilitating enhancement in flavour and mouth feel when used in food preparation. Due to these properties, the protein probably could be used as a functional ingredient in foods. The results of the other functional properties; foaming capacity, foaming stability, Emulsion capacity, Emulsion stability all followed the same trend of MPFPC having highest values for such parameters followed by DMPFF. Emulsion stability (ES) and fat binding during processing are primary functional properties of protein in such foods as comminuted meat products. MPFPC, which has the highest foam capacity, could be due to its higher protein content. Protein in the dispersion may cause a lowering of the surface tension at the water air interface, always due to protein which forms a continuous cohesive film around the air bubbles in the foam (Kaushal *et al.*, 2012). Both DMPFF and MPFPC formed a gel at a significantly higher concentration (13 g/ 100 ml). This could be accounted for as a result of the fact that these products contain high protein and starch content since the gelation capacity of flours is influenced by physical competition for water between protein gelation and starch gelatinization (Kaushal *et al.*, 2012) and that explains why WMPFF with lower protein content ($6.77\% \pm 0.77$) formed gel quickly at a lowest concentration (7 g/100 ml) while DMPFF and MPFPC with protein content of 21.43 ± 1.34 and 40.32 ± 1.54 respectively formed gel at highest concentration (13 g/100 ml) each.

Photochemical properties of whole moriche palm fruit flour (WMPFF), defatted moriche palm fruit flour (DMPFF) and moriche palm fruit protein concentrate (MPFPC)

The results of Phytochemical Properties of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC are as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Phytochemical properties of moriche palm fruit flours

Phytochemical Property	WMPFF	DMPFF	MPFPC
Saponin (mg/ g)	24.04±0.88 ^a	13.55±0.34 ^b	3.05±0.05 ^c
Tannin (mg/g)	15.43±0.67 ^a	11.93±0.08 ^b	3.44±0.32 ^c
Steroids (mg/g)	1.34±0.05 ^a	1.11±0.43 ^b	0.63±0.08 ^c
Total phenolic content (mgGAE/g)	54.32±1.43 ^a	23.22±1.54 ^b	7.43±0.34 ^c
Alkaloids (%)	19.65±0.67 ^a	11.77±0.78 ^b	4.66±0.08 ^c
Flavonoids (mgRUTIN/g)	42.45±1.55 ^a	13.79±0.09 ^b	6.44±0.22 ^c

Values are means± S.D triplicate determinations. Means within each row not followed by the same superscript letters are significantly different ($p < 0.05$), MPFWF= moriche palm fruit whole flour, DMPFF = defatted moriche palm fruit flour and MPFPC = moriche palm fruit protein concentrate

From Table 4, it can be seen that saponin, tannin and steroids content of the products ranged from 3.05±0.05 to 24.04±0.88 mg/g, 3.44±0.32 to 15.43±0.67mg/g and 0.63±0.08 to 1.34±0.05 mg/g respectively while Total phenolic content and Alkaloids content ranged from 7.43±0.34 to 54.32±1.43 mgGAE/g and 4.66±0.08 to 19.65±0.67% respectively.

Flavonoids content of the three products ranged from 6.44 ± 0.22 to 42.45 ± 1.55 mgRUTIN/g. The result shows that there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in all the parameters for the three products with WMPFF having the highest values followed by DMPFF while MPFPC had the lowest values.

DPPH radical scavenging activity (DRSA) of MPFWF, DMPFF and MPFPC

DPPH is a synthetic free radical that is relatively stable and can accept electron or hydroxyl radical when it interacts with natural bioactive compounds to become a less reactive, more stable molecule (Girgih *et al.*, 2014). Due to its relative stability, DPPH radical has been widely used to test the ability of natural compounds or extracts from plant and animal sources to act as free radical scavengers or hydrogen donors (Dontha, 2016). Figure 1A shows the ability of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC to scavenge DPPH radical. All the samples exhibited reasonable DRSA which ranged from 37 to 55% when compared to the GSH positive control standard (66%). It was observed that DRSA increased with processing; WMPFF had the lowest DRSA (37%) followed by DMPFF (44%) and MPFPC had the highest DRSA (55%). The increase in the DPPH radical scavenging activities of the DMPFF and MPFPC could be attributed to substantial amounts of hydrophobic amino acids in the samples (45% and 46% for DMPFF and MPFPC respectively as compared to 42% for WMPFF) as well as reasonable increase in the NCAAs in the processed moriche palm fruit flours which have been reported to contribute to strong antioxidant properties (Aondona *et al.*, 2020). In general, the DRSA of food products depends on a variety of factors such as processing methods, species, amino acid composition of the peptides, and the DPPH assay conditions (Aondona *et al.*, 2020). The DRSA of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC may be due to the presence or availability of electron donors that reduced the free radicals to more stable inert molecules. In addition, several studies have demonstrated that hydrophobic amino acids act as antioxidants by increasing the solubility of peptides in non-polar environments thereby facilitating better interaction with free radicals (such as DPPH) and terminating their reactivity (Aondona *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, the DRSA of moriche palm fruit flours were higher (37% – 55%) than those reported for Reversed-phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) separated salmon peptide fractions (9% – 33%), which were also evaluated at 1mg peptide/ml (Girgih *et al.*, 2013) and also higher than those reported by Girgih *et al.*, 2014 for cod protein hydrolysate (17% – 32%) at same 1mg/ml of the sample. The trend of the DPPH results of the moriche palm fruit flours disagrees with the results by Virgolin *et al.* (2017) whereby the antioxidant activity (DPPH) in some fruits was highly correlated with total-phenolic compound content and those obtained by Shafii *et al.*, 2017 that the antioxidant activity (DPPH scavenging activity) of some fruits had a good correlation with phenolic and flavonoid content $R^2 = 0.9905$ and $R^2 = 0.9924$. These results were also in disagreement with those obtained by Bedawey *et al.*, (2010) who found that highly positive relationship existed between total phenolics and antioxidant activity in many plant species as the DMPFF and MPFPC with lower phenolic content of 23% and 7% respectively and flavonoid contents; 14% and 6% respectively which were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the phenolic and flavonoid content of the WMPFF; 54% and 42% respectively had higher DRSA values of 43% and 55% than the DRSA for WMPFF (37%). This result suggests that the bioactive components of the samples are not the only determining factor for increased level of antioxidant properties of any food sample,

but the amino acid composition also has a significant contributing factor in determining the antioxidant properties as can be observed.

FIGURE 1 (A) DPPH radical scavenging activities (DRSA) (B) Superoxide radical scavenging activities (SRSA) (C) Hydroxyl radical scavenging activities (HRSA) of whole moriche palm fruit flour (WMPFF), Defatted moriche palm fruit flour (DMPFF) and moriche palm fruit protein concentrate (MPFPC) in comparison to the standard antioxidant glutathione (GSH). Bars with different alphabets are significantly different at $p < .05$

SRSA of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

The superoxide radical is an *in vivo* anion radical that promotes oxidative reactions causing a reduction in transition metals and its further reaction with the hydroxyl radical leads to the damage of cellular organelles such as DNA, cell membrane lipids, proteins, and enzymes (Elias *et al.*, 2008; Engwa, 2018; Kurutas, 2015, Aondona *et al.*, 2020). These radicals are generated by a number of biological reactions during normal physiological activities. The body's endogenous mechanism for the control of superoxide radical is by use of endogenous enzyme called superoxide dismutase which catalyzes the neutralization and conversion into hydrogen peroxide and oxygen, however, under diseased state, excessive amounts are produced by the body that could indirectly initiate lipid oxidation and cause cell damage (Ighodaro & Akinloye, 2018, Aondona *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, scavenging of these radicals would be of great importance as it would go a long way in reducing their destructive tendencies toward biological molecules leading to the development of oxidative stress-related disease conditions. The SRSA of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC are shown in Figure 1B. The processed moriche palm fruit flours; DMPFF and MPFPC have significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher SRSA values of 24% and 32% respectively as compared to that of WMPFF (18%) but are however significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than that of the GSH (58%). Hydrophobicity is one of the factors that determine the superoxide scavenging activities, however, the presence of higher levels of electron-donating amino acids seem to contribute to better SRSA (Girgih *et al.*, 2014). Thus, the significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the SRSA for DMPFF and MPFPC could be explained partly as a result of increased levels of HAA (45% and 46%) and partly as a result of increasing levels of NAA (28% and 25%) for the DMPFF

and MPFPC respectively when compared to significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower values of HAA (42%) and NAA (23%) for WMPFF. From the results, it can be observed that the ability to donate electrons is an important feature for improved scavenging of superoxide radicals. The SRSA data obtained for moriche palm fruit flours follow the same trend as those previously reported for salmon (Girgih *et al.*, 2013), pea (Pownall, 2010) sesame flours (Aondona *et al.*, 2020) where increased levels of HAA and NCAA led to increased scavenging of superoxide radicals at the same level of sample concentration (1 mg/ml).

HRSA of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

The hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC is shown in Figure 1C. Hydroxyl radical is one of the most reactive ROS. Superoxide anion can be converted *in vivo* by the action of Superoxide dismutase (Dismutation), to produce hydrogen peroxide which is then converted in presence of transition metal ions to hydroxyl radical. On the other hand, hydroxyl radical could also be generated from other radical systems resulting in lipid peroxidation (Girgih *et al.*, 2011; Phaniendra *et al.*, 2015; Aondona *et al.*, 2020). Lipid peroxidation involves a hydroxyl radical abstracting an electron from unsaturated fatty acids. This creates an unstable lipid radical which can react with oxygen forming a fatty acid peroxy radical. Repeated cycles of lipid peroxidation due to accumulation of hydroxyl radicals cause serious damage to cell membranes, DNA, proteins, enzymes and tissues leading to development of chronic diseases such as diabetes, cancer and cardiovascular diseases (CVD). The scavenging of hydroxyl radicals is, therefore, an effective defense strategy of the human body system against the etiology of various chronic diseases linked to the damaging activities of free radicals (Lipinski, 2011). The type of free radical system utilized for antioxidant evaluation could influence experimental results; thus, the use of more than one free radical system to investigate radical-scavenging capacities of a selected antioxidant has been recommended and hence the use of HRSA as one of them frequently used (Jan *et al.*, 2013; Aondona *et al.*, 2020). The scavenging activities of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC were compared to GSH. WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC had hydroxyl radical scavenging activities of 14%, 24% and 36% respectively which were lower than that of GSH which scavenged 49% hydroxyl radical.

MCA of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

The metal chelation assay evaluates the ability of peptides to form complexes with transition metals (such as Fe^{2+} and Cu^{2+}) that catalyze and promote lipid peroxidation, making them unavailable to participate in reactions that lead to generation of ROS and free radicals. Protein Peptides have been reported to act as indirect antioxidant agents through their chelating activities with metal ions, which ultimately reduce the susceptibility of lipids to oxidative peroxidation and associated negative health effects (Girgih *et al.*, 2011, Girgih *et al.*, 2014). Chelating agents may serve as secondary antioxidants because they reduce the redox potential, hence stabilizing the oxidized form of the metal ions. The Fe^{2+} chelating ability was estimated in this study by decrease in the absorbance of ferrozine- Fe^{2+} complex after the addition of the test samples. Figure 2A shows the metal Chelating effects of reduced GSH, WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC. It can be observed that WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC all showed significant MCA with the MPFPC exhibiting the strongest (64%) which was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than those of the WMPFF (44%) and DMPFF (53%). The significant MCA of the WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC could be attributed partly to

the high levels of NCAAs; 23%, 28% and 25% in WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC respectively which could have contributed to increased electrostatic affinity for the positively charged ions.

Ferric ion reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC

FRAP is usually used to evaluate the capacity of natural antioxidants to donate hydrogen or transfer electrons to transition metals responsible for catalyzing the formation of harmful ROS/ free radicals. Previous research works have shown a direct correlation between enhanced antioxidant activities (measured as inhibition of ROS production) and the reducing power of natural peptides (Tang *et al.* 2012, Cheng *et al.*, 2006; Wang *et al.*, 2007). In this assay, the ability of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC to reduce Ferric ion (Fe^{3+}) to Ferrous ion (Fe^{2+}) was determined through changes in the absorbance at 700 nm of the supernatant of the reaction mixture: the higher the absorbance, the stronger the metal reducing power of the sample. The FRAP of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC is as shown in Table 2B. While GSH had FRAP value of 0.516%, WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC had FRAP values ranged from 0.0893% – 0.322% with WMPFF showing the strongest FRAP (0.322 absorbance) followed by DMPFF (0.167 absorbance) and MPFPC showed the lowest FRAP (0.0893 absorbance).

FIGURE 2: (A) Metal chelating activity (MCA) and (B) Ferric ion reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) of WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC in comparison to the standard antioxidant glutathione (GSH). Bars with different alphabets are significantly different at $p < .05$.

Conclusion

This study investigated Chemical, Functional and in vitro antioxidant Properties of Moriche Palm (*Mauritia flexuosa*) Fruit Flours; WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC. Results have shown that DMPFF and MPFPC are good sources of carbohydrates and proteins. The three products all contain the 20 amino acids and have strong in vitro antioxidant properties as evident in their strong radical scavenging and metal binding activities though lower when compared to the standard Glutathione (GSH). The moriche palm fruit products (WMPFF, DMPFF and MPFPC) were able to scavenge free radicals, which was demonstrated using DRSA, SRSA, and HRSA assays. Radical scavenging activities were stronger for DPPH and hydroxyl than the superoxide. In addition, moriche palm fruit products were able to reduce Fe^{3+} and chelate Fe^{2+} , which could reduce the ability of these ions to promote formation of toxic free radicals. This study also revealed that scavenging radical and metal chelation activities were higher for MPFPC and DMPFF than for WMPFF.

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